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*GOOD PRACTICES AND CHALLENGES IN SALES MANAGEMENT:
CONTRIBUTIONS FROM PLUS-SIZE CLOTHING STORES IN SÃO JOSÉ
DOS CAMPOS¹*

**BOAS PRÁTICAS E DIFICULDADE NA GESTÃO DE VENDAS:
CONTRIBUIÇÕES DE LOJAS DE ROUPAS PLUS SIZE DE SÃO JOSÉ DOS
CAMPOS**

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ABSTRACT

There is significant complexity, competitiveness, and dynamism in the market, where companies face numerous challenges to remain relevant and profitable. This qualitative study analyzes the good practices and challenges in sales management for clothing stores of São José dos Campos. The objective is to propose recommendations to improve sales results in the women's plus-size fashion textile sector. The study identified best practices such as following fashion trends, enhancing product value, and implementing effective marketing strategies. On the other hand, challenges included high prices, a restricted target audience, and the lack of an attractive store layout. As limitations, the research

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encountered a scarcity of stores in this segment within São José dos Campos and difficulties in finding adequate materials for a deeper market analysis.

Keywords: sales management, plus size fashion, clothing stores, competitiveness, textile industry.

RESUMO

Existe uma grande complexidade, competitividade e dinamicidade no mercado, onde as empresas enfrentam inúmeros desafios para se manterem relevantes e lucrativas. Este trabalho numa abordagem qualitativa analisa as boas práticas e dificuldades da gestão de vendas em lojas de roupas em São José dos Campos. O estudo tem como objetivo propor recomendações para melhoria dos resultados de venda nas empresas do segmento têxtil de moda feminina *plus size*. Foi possível observar como boas práticas as tendências de moda, valorização do produto e estratégias de *marketing*. Identificou-se como dificuldades o preço elevado, público-alvo restrito e falta de *layout* atrativo. Como limitações, a pesquisa enfrentou a escassez de lojas desse segmento na cidade de São José dos Campos e a dificuldade em encontrar materiais adequados para uma análise mais profunda do mercado.

Palavras chaves: gestão de vendas, moda *plus size*, lojas de roupa, competitividade, indústria têxtil.

INTRODUCTION

According to Parente (2000, p. 201), fashion affects all retail sectors to varying degrees. However, its influence is especially intense in apparel retailing. In general, the life cycle of fashion-related products tends to be shorter and less predictable (Caczmareki, 2008).

The need to develop new products depends on the company's target market, the sector in which it operates, and its position in the value chain. For many companies, the capacity for innovation - whether in terms of performance or product design - is a fundamental factor for their competitive capability. Nevertheless, regardless of market- and sector-related factors, the development of new products and services is a common characteristic across all supply network processes, ranging from the development of new fibers to the

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development of new solutions in the areas of distribution and procurement (Oliveira, 2015).

The textile industry, due to its production chain, shows a strong tendency toward growth both in production and in its participation in international trade as a whole. As the population's per capita income increases, textile consumption will certainly grow (Cavalcanti, 2022).

When discussing importance within the organization, the sales area is a key part of the evolution of a company's strategy. According to Megido (2002), throughout Brazilian history, commercial capability has always been associated with achieved progress, while sales incompetence has consistently been linked to a lack of progress. In Megido's (2002) view, sales is an activity that accompanies people throughout life and becomes inevitable in any area of human experience. Within organizations, it is essential to study commercial management practices and models, as the lack of such understanding is the cause of many business failures.

According to Ledingham, Kovack, and Simon (2006), personal selling has evolved into a scientific approach based on four dimensions that make performance improvement predictable and controllable. This new scientific approach, which is the focus of this study, seeks to increase the productivity of the sales team. According to the authors, this approach begins with the process of offering and directing products and services, adapting them to the needs of each market segment, while ensuring that the right product is being sold to the right customer.

According to Ingram et al. (2008), sales management is understood as the management of an organization's personal selling function. Sales managers are involved in both the strategic and operational aspects of personal selling, as well as in activities related to its evaluation and control. Among managers' responsibilities, their ability to effectively deal with people in the personal selling

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function, with individuals in other functional areas of the organization, and with people outside the organization - especially customers - stands out.

Leigh and Marshall (2001) believe that the challenges currently faced by sales organizations will continue to increase. The authors state that successful organizations will be those willing to change and confront these challenges. Trends are related to a more strategic perspective regarding sales organizations, as they seek to adopt a market-oriented approach. According to Leigh and Marshall (2001), it is necessary to change the activities of managers and salespeople for the organization to be successful in a strategic role.

Thus, the research question proposed in this study is: How can women's clothing stores in the plus-size segment improve their sales performance by using advanced commercialization techniques? Based on this question, the objectives of the study are to propose recommendations for improving sales results in companies within the plus-size women's fashion textile segment; to identify the main theoretical elements of best practices and difficulties in the sales management of clothing stores; and to analyze the main best practices and difficulties faced by women's clothing stores in the plus-size segment.

JUSTIFICATON

There is great complexity, competitiveness, and dynamism in the market, where companies face numerous challenges to remain relevant and profitable. Small and medium-sized enterprises, in particular, suffer the most, as they face significant challenges in competing with large, well-established brands.

With a focus on the fashion market, this study will highlight the importance - especially for small and medium-sized enterprises - of using effective sales management strategies and how essential they are for business growth and survival. Efficient companies endure, survive, and grow, while less efficient ones decline and may eventually dissolve (Machado, 2016).

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THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This section contains the subsections textile industry, sales management, and clothing stores.

Textile industry

The textile industry encompasses activities ranging from the production of raw materials to the manufacture of the final product. It is present in most countries because it meets one of the main human needs – clothing - and reflects people's apparel preferences (Fujita; Jorente, 2015). Textile industries are of great importance to the economy due to their high sales volume and because they generate approximately 1.5 million direct jobs and 8 million indirect jobs in Brazil, of which 75% are female workers. This represents about 16.7% of jobs in the manufacturing industry, making textiles the second-largest employing sector in the country, with the food and beverage sector being the largest employer (Filleti; Boldrin, 2020).

Brazilian textile industries rank as the fifth-largest textile industry globally and the fourth-largest in the apparel segment. Even so, they produce less and import more, especially textile products manufactured by Chinese companies, as a result of the dominance of Chinese industries in this field (Filleti; Boldrin, 2020). Their operations involve the production and export of raw materials - cotton, fibers, and synthetic fibers; the transformation of these raw materials into yarns, knits, and fabrics; and the manufacture of final products for retail. Yarn and knitwear industries, in order to remain competitive, depend on investment and technology, while apparel manufacturing companies operate by reproducing new standards set by leading fashion companies. This process involves analyzing current trends and selecting materials and aesthetic combinations for the launch

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of an annual collection. Understanding the rapid changes in consumer tastes is a key characteristic of these companies (Monteiro Filha; Santos, 2002).

In this context, it is possible to identify best practices in the textile industry, including eco-friendly production methods such as water and fabric scrap reuse; the use of sustainable materials that are less harmful to the environment (Martins, 2019); automation and digitalization of processes to minimize waste and improve quality; investment in high-quality machinery, such as equipment with lower energy consumption (FCEM, 2018); and the appreciation of human capital through safe working conditions and continuous training, as the industry depends on an abundant and well-trained workforce (Monteiro Filha; Santos, 2002).

However, the sector also faces significant challenges. By analyzing the trajectory of the Brazilian textile industry, it is possible to identify strong potential for creation and innovation; nevertheless, this potential faces barriers due to insufficient investment in machinery, equipment, and technology, which also results in difficulties in keeping up with the constant changes in consumer preferences (Fujita; Jorente, 2015). Furthermore, the small size of many Brazilian textile companies leads to a lack of critical mass to compete internationally, especially against Asian countries, which benefit from low-cost labor, better structural conditions for cost reduction, and a high level of control over the stages of production, design, and marketing, thereby promoting their dominance in the Brazilian market (Santos, 2005).

Textile industries operate across various segments, as all products made from fabrics originate in the textile market. The main sectors associated with the textile industry include the automotive sector, which uses fabrics for car upholstery; the decoration and furniture sector, where fabrics are used to produce curtains, rugs, and furniture; the household goods sector, in which fabrics are used to manufacture items such as aprons, cloths, towels, and sheets; the

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technical textiles sector, for hospital and industrial use; the sports and leisure products sector; and the fashion/apparel sector, which is the focus of this study, where clothing, footwear, and accessories are made primarily from textiles (Fujita; Jorente, 2015).

Sales management

Sales management (SM) can be defined as one of the crucial aspects for companies seeking growth and profitability. It involves a set of activities such as planning, directing, and controlling the activities involved in sales processes, from pre-sales to after-sales (Dias et al., n.d.). In addition, sales management can be understood as the process of developing the sales force, coordinating operations, and implementing sales techniques, enabling the company to generate revenue consistently in order to achieve its goals. Sales processes are structured around the identification, approach, and closing of business opportunities.

Sales management is a management area that focuses on the practical application of sales techniques and the administration of commercial departments. In short, sales management is fundamental to driving a company's growth and success; its objective is to generate greater process efficiency so that sales activities are effective, efficient, meet customer needs, provide a positive experience, and strengthen the customer–company relationship (Dias et al., n.d.).

The implementation of sales management involves a series of practices that may vary according to the specific needs of the company. It is important to analyze the market, competition, industry trends, and customer behavior in order to implement sales management. This implementation requires time, effort, and commitment, but it can result in significant improvements in sales performance and business growth.

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Sales management brings several benefits to organizations. First, it tends to maximize sales and, consequently, revenue through well-planned and well-executed strategies that direct sales efforts efficiently. This results in high-quality customer service, which increases customer satisfaction and loyalty. In addition, the use of well-defined processes and CRM tools automates repetitive tasks, allowing salespeople to focus on higher value-added activities, thereby improving efficiency and productivity.

There are also several challenges in sales management, such as a lack of planning, agility, training, and team development, as well as bureaucratic processes and communication failures in customer relationships. These issues can lead to delays and dissatisfaction, hindering positive sales results. The impacts can be significant, as effective sales management should ensure business success, while ineffective management can result in low sales and loss of market share (Angnes et al., 2012).

The problem of sales management arises when a company is unable to effectively manage the sales process and customer interactions throughout the entire cycle. This scenario can result in lost sales, dissatisfied customers, high sales costs, and a negative impact on the brand image.

When we refer to “cascading” in the context of sales management, we generally mean the process of breaking down sales goals into smaller, more specific targets distributed across different hierarchical levels within the sales organization. This is done to ensure that each team member understands their contribution to overall sales goals and knows exactly what is expected of them. Cascading sales goals is a common and effective practice to ensure that everyone in the sales organization is aligned and focused on working together to achieve the company’s objectives. It also helps create accountability and motivation among team members, as they have a clear understanding of their responsibilities and the role they play in the company’s overall success.

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Clothing stores

Clothing stores are environments whose purpose is to display and sell garments from specific brands and/or collections. Within this environment, various segmentations are presented according to the gender and age of the target audience and the style of clothing intended for sale - casual, formal, sportswear, among others. Clothing stores can operate in two different formats: physical stores and online stores.

In general, physical stores operate by displaying garments on mannequins and racks, showcasing different sizes, colors, and styles. This allows customers to access a wide variety of items and choose those best suited to their body type and size. Some physical stores provide fitting rooms to assist customers in the decision-making process, as well as staff members who can accompany and support consumers during their purchase.

Online stores, in turn, operate through a website and/or the store's social media platforms, where the entire display process is carried out through photographs. Product information - such as size, price, and color options - is provided in the product descriptions. Product selection, customer service, and payment are all conducted virtually. In this way, customers receive their orders at home, or, in some cases, companies offer the option of in-store pickup.

In a clothing store, prioritizing the customer experience is crucial. This means creating a welcoming and pleasant environment in which customers feel comfortable exploring the products. The staff should be trained to provide courteous, helpful, and knowledgeable service, ensuring that customers receive assistance when needed. To understand customers and remain attentive to market changes, companies in the textile sector must invest in market research, marketing planning, and the development of strong brands (Martins, 2003). Product variety also plays a fundamental role; it is important to maintain a

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diversified inventory that includes a wide range of styles, sizes, and colors to meet different customer preferences. In this type of retail, there is differentiated visual merchandising, with an emphasis on the enhancement and segmentation of products by category, gender, lifestyle, and age (De Avelar Junior, 2014).

Marketing strategies are essential to attract customers to the store. These may include promotions, special events, and advertising campaigns, as well as maintaining a strong presence on social media to engage customers and promote products. Effective inventory management is crucial to ensure product availability and avoid problems of overstocking or shortages. This includes maintaining accurate inventory control and monitoring sales trends in order to make adjustments as needed. To meet the demands of this new consumer, department stores developed a strategic model that shortened the time it takes for new fashion items to reach stores. This model was called fast fashion, in reference to the reduced cycles of development and commercialization of fashion apparel (De Avelar Junior, 2014).

Clothing stores face a series of complex challenges that directly impact their operations and success in the market. One of the main difficulties is intense competition, with numerous brands and stores competing for consumer attention. In addition, the volatile nature of fashion trends requires these stores to remain constantly updated and aligned with customer preferences, which can be difficult to predict and follow. Effective inventory management is also essential to avoid financial losses due to excess products or shortages of popular items, as these models have a very short life cycle in stores, since inventories consist of small batches with only a few units produced for each style (De Avelar Junior, 2014).

High operating costs, such as rent and employee salaries, represent another significant barrier, especially in a competitive market. Furthermore, seasonal sales and the growing impact of e-commerce add additional pressure to physical stores. Offering a satisfactory shopping experience - including high-

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quality customer service and flexible return policies - is essential to attract and retain customers. Finally, issues related to sizing and fit may pose additional challenges for consumers, requiring stores to provide a wide range of options and personalized services.

A clothing store is a complex ecosystem that requires attention to many details, from business model and marketing strategies to inventory management and customer experience. Considering legal, financial, technological, and sustainability aspects is crucial for success and longevity in the market. The ability to continuously adapt and innovate will allow clothing stores to remain competitive and relevant in an ever-evolving industry.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study was developed based on a qualitative approach, as it seeks to deepen the understanding of sales management rather than represent it numerically (Goldenberg, 1997, p. 34).

The research consists of a multiple case study conducted in three plus-size clothing stores within the authors' area of reach (in the São José dos Campos region, São Paulo, Brazil). With this approach, the research can be classified as exploratory and applied, as it aims to formulate hypotheses on the topic as well as generate knowledge for practical application, directed toward solving specific problems (Gil, 2002). This research was carried out according to the methodological flow presented in Figure 1, and its stages are described below.

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Figure 1 – Methodological Flow

Source: Authors (2024)

In Phase 1, the research question to be answered, the objectives to be achieved, and the method used to conduct the study are defined.

In Phase 2, three elements are identified: the data protocol, the conduct of the case studies, and the cross-case analysis. The first element consists of the development of the data protocol, which is presented in detail in the Appendix A.

The second element refers to the on-site execution of the case studies. This stage involved visiting each of the stores selected as objects of study in order to conduct interviews with the managers and individuals responsible for the establishments. The interviews addressed the sales channels used by the stores, the sales and marketing techniques identified within the companies, the infrastructure of the establishments, as well as the differentiating factors offered by each store. Thus, the authors aimed to carry out direct on-site analysis and collect the necessary data to continue the research.

The third element consists of the cross-case analysis, which was influenced by the collected data, the evidence observed during on-site visits, and the documentary analysis of what the establishments offer - such as social media and websites - conducted by the authors.

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Finally, in Phase 3, the conclusions are presented, clearly outlining the answer to the research question, the objectives achieved, the contributions made, the limitations encountered, and suggestions for future studies.

CROSS-CASE ANALYSIS

This subsection will analyze the main best practices and difficulties identified in women's plus-size clothing stores, based on multiple case studies conducted in three stores in São José dos Campos, in the state of São Paulo. The characterization of these stores is described in Chart 1.

Chart 1 – Characterization of stores

Elements	Instrument for data collection		
	A	B	C
Time of market	5 years	7 years	1 year
Localization	Vila Ema - Southeast	Centre	Centre
Type of store	Neighborhood store	Mall store	Shopping store

Source: Authors (2024)

Chart 2 presents the clusters, their specific elements, and the respective authors of the articles from which these elements were taken.

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Chart 2 – Theoretical definition of data collection protocol

Cluster	Elements	Authors
Sales Channels	Social Networks	do Prado e Lourenço (2024)
	Own Website	
	Third-Party Website	
	Physical Store	
	Good accessibility of online sales channels	
	After-sales service	
Sales Techniques	Prospecting	Silva et al. (2009)
	Salesperson Training	
	Promotions and Benefits	
	Trend Analysis	
Marketing Techniques	CRM (Customer Relationship Management)	Coelho (2022)
	Benchmarking	
	Marketing Plan	
	Market Segmentation	
	Servqual	
Management	Do returns and exchanges impact the store's inventory management?	Oliveira e Silva (2014) e Terrence; Escrivão Filho (2001)
	Does the company set monthly sales targets?	
Competitive Advantage	Low Price (budget)	de Avelar Junior (2014)
	Copypat	
	Fantasy	
Layout	Fitting Rooms	Pacheco, Binsely e Cavalcanti (2017)
	Mirrors throughout the store	
	Easy access to products	
	Comfortable seating area	
	Eye-catching window displays	
Employee Posture	Does the team have appropriate attire and posture?	Júnior, Cardoso e Iwaya (2020)

Source: Authors (2024)

In this category, the authors prioritized including data that identifies good practices implemented by the stores, based on interviews with managers and physical characteristics observed on-site. The identified elements are marked with an “x”.

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Chart 3 – Identificação dos casos

Elements	A	B	C
Social Networks	X	X	X
Own Website	X		
Third-Party Website			
Physical Store	X	X	X
Good accessibility of online sales channels	X	X	X
After-sales service	X	X	X
Prospecting	X		
Salesperson Training	X		X
Promotions and Benefits	X	X	X
Trend Analysis	X	X	X
CRM (Customer Relationship Management)	X	X	X
Benchmarking		X	X
Marketing Plan	X		X
Market Segmentation	X		
Servqual			X
Do returns and exchanges impact the store's inventory management?		X	X
Does the company set monthly sales targets?	X	X	X
Low Price (budget)			
Copycat		X	
Fantasy	X	X	X
Fitting Rooms	X	X	X
Mirrors throughout the store	X	X	X
Easy access to products	X	X	X
Comfortable seating area	X	X	
Eye-catching window displays	X		
Does the team have appropriate attire and posture?	X	X	

Source: Authors (2024)

With regard to the Sales Channels cluster, it was found that only Company A has its own website; however, all three companies are active on social media, using this medium as one of their main sales channels. The importance of being present on social networks lies in the development of a company's identity and market positioning, the wide reach and good relationship with the public, and, consequently, increased sales (SEBRAE, 2023). Due to globalization, the internet has become the most important means of communication for organizations (Silva et al., 2019). In 2019, only 35% of customer service interactions were carried out through digital channels; by

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October 2022, this figure had risen to 81%, demonstrating that adapting to social media today is not only important but necessary (Do Prado & Lourenço, 2024).

All three companies also offer accessible online sales channels, through which customers learn to interact digitally with the company, focusing on routine issues such as requesting duplicate invoices, and come to view the physical store as a channel for resolving very specific or critical problems (Do Prado & Lourenço, 2024). They also provide after-sales service, which is of utmost importance for achieving higher profit margins and for establishing a strong and growing relationship with customers, with a focus on an environment geared toward consumer loyalty and satisfaction (Giacobo, Estrada & Ceretta, 2003).

Regarding Sales Techniques, it was observed that all three companies use promotions and trend analysis. In terms of sales force training, Companies A and C prepare their employees according to the specifications of their future positions, and only Company A uses prospecting in addition to the other techniques. Prospecting consists of identifying potential customers with a focus on results (Da Silva Pereira, 2017). Sales techniques play a crucial role in companies, as they support better communication and customer loyalty by providing personalized service. Moreover, they act as powerful tools for achieving commercial success (Moskit CRM, 2024).

In Marketing, Company A analyzes market segmentation, a tool for identifying target audiences and developing strategies focused on specific interest groups, while Company C uses SERVQUAL, which analyzes customer expectations and perceptions across five dimensions of service quality: tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. In addition, both companies develop a marketing plan containing data on market trends and characteristics, aimed at identifying which resources the company can invest in. Companies B and C conduct benchmarking, comparing themselves with other companies and using them as references to achieve better results, and all three

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companies apply CRM, or relationship marketing (Coelho, 2022). It is essential for salespeople to understand the factors that lead consumers to choose their brand over competitors; for this reason, marketing techniques become extremely important for companies because, when applied effectively, they establish products and services in the market and in consumers' minds, leveraging business growth (Santos & Silva, 2023).

In the Management cluster, issues related to inventory and targets were addressed. In Stores B and C, returns and exchanges impact inventory management, whereas Company A handles such returns effectively. Good inventory management is of paramount importance for any company, as it improves customer service, acts as a buffer between demand and supply, and serves as protection against price increases and contingencies (Oliveira & Da Silva, 2014). In addition, all three companies set targets by product and/or defined periods, which are reviewed whenever necessary. Establishing monthly goals or goals by clothing collections helps companies guide their strategies, aiming to understand their reach and what needs to be adjusted to achieve the final objective (Terrence & Escrivão Filho, 2001).

To establish competitive advantage, Companies A, B, and C employ the fantasy technique, introducing innovation into their products to add value and quality, while only Company B uses the copycat technique, a method of copying a leading store in the segment in order to demonstrate that its products have equivalent quality (De Avelar Junior, 2014). Investing in competitive advantage is important and necessary, as it makes products or services more attractive to customers, encouraging purchases even in the face of problems, crisis situations, or a lack of certain resources (SEBRAE, 2023).

Issues related to store layout were analyzed in person, and it was concluded that all stores have fitting rooms and mirrors, as well as easy access to products. However, Companies A and B also provide a lounge area and staff

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with appropriate posture and attire, while only Company A features an eye-catching storefront display. The environment is one of the most significant aspects and, in some cases, can have a greater influence than the product itself on purchase decisions. Therefore, having a good layout is important and necessary. In addition to influencing purchase completion, the proper arrangement of furniture and store spaces meets the needs of consumers and their companions, as well as those of employees. Thus, store layout enhances the shopping experience, increasing customer dwell time and, consequently, company sales (Pacheco, Binsley & Cavalcanti, 2017).

CONCLUSION

Interviews were conducted with managers of plus-size clothing stores, through which the information necessary to carry out a cross-case analysis of data on the main best practices and difficulties faced by each store was collected, with the aim of achieving the study's objective.

Based on the case studies, it was identified that the main best practices involve accessible online sales channels, greater ease of promotion, strong market positioning (favored by visibility on social media), product valorization, strategies focused on groups with higher purchasing power, trend analysis, and close relationships with customers through the application of CRM techniques.

Regarding the difficulties faced by the stores, these include high product prices, a limited target audience, an unattractive layout, the absence of a proprietary website, and product returns, which directly impact inventory management. This challenge generally affects the control of inbound and outbound merchandise.

It is understood that offering quality service and treating customers with respect is essential. During each sale, a high-quality approach is required to

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increase profits and establish lasting bonds with consumers, with an emphasis on customer loyalty and satisfaction.

To stand out in a competitive market, it is important for businesses to find unique ways to differentiate themselves. In the specific case of a store focused on larger sizes, cultivating a strong identity and adopting an efficient strategy to attract and retain customers is fundamental. Offering superior-quality products represents a significant competitive advantage, requiring skillful management in product presentation and the creation of an attractive environment for consumers.

With regard to layout, space arrangement is crucial and may influence purchase decisions even more than the product itself. A well-planned environment directly impacts buying behavior while also meeting the needs of customers, companions, and employees. Therefore, a well-designed store enhances the shopping experience, extends the length of customer stay, and consequently boosts sales.

It is concluded that the research question was answered by organizing and analyzing the main aspects that identify and define the key best practices and difficulties faced by women's plus-size clothing stores.

The plus-size market is characterized by a lack of diversity in store options and in the availability of quality clothing at affordable prices. These items are generally expensive due to the production costs of larger-size garments and the limited selection of collections. Thus, finding affordable prices in this sector represents both a financial and social achievement. For plus-size stores, affordable pricing goes beyond revenue considerations, as it has a direct impact on customers' self-esteem and well-being. When individuals can purchase products that meet their physical needs and fit within their budget, they feel more confident, and the shopping experience becomes more complete and enjoyable. When cost ceases to be a barrier, shopping becomes more inclusive.

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In this way, the contributions of the study assist in a more precise definition of the term “sales management.” The research aimed to identify the most important aspects for developing specific sales techniques for apparel stores in the plus-size niche.

As a limitation, there was a scarcity of plus-size stores in São José dos Campos, resulting in an unsatisfactory response rate from the few stores contacted. In addition, difficulty in finding suitable materials for the study was a limiting factor in the development of the research, preventing a more comprehensive assessment of the market.

The study sought to analyze issues related to sales management and to identify additional topics for future research. Due to the unavailability of certain information, future studies are recommended to: further deepen research on sales management; explore the impact of best practices on customer satisfaction; develop new studies to improve the sales management process; and investigate the adoption of new CRM technologies in the textile industry.

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Appendix A – Protocol for collecting research data

Elements	Data Collection Instrument		
	Structured interview	On-site observation	Document analysis
Social media	X		
Own website	X		
Third-party website	X		
Physical store	X		
Good accessibility of online sales channels			X
Does the store offer after-sales service?	X		
Prospecting	X		
Salesperson training	X		
Promotions and benefits	X		
Trend analysis	X		
CRM (Customer Relationship Management)	X		
Benchmarking	X		
Marketing plan	X		
Market segmentation	X		
Servqual	X		
Do returns and exchanges impact the store's inventory management?	X		
Does the company set monthly sales targets?	X		
Low price (budget)	X		
Copycat	X		
Fantasy	X		
Fitting booths		X	
Mirrors throughout the store		X	
Easy access to products		X	
Seating area		X	
Eye-catching window displays		X	
Does the team have appropriate attire and posture?		X	

Source: Authors (2024)